

Behaviour theories literature review

Report

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Introduction

The ways in which values and behaviour interact are arguably central to the motivation for this IPBES Values Assessment. First, many valuation processes rest on fundamental assumptions that better articulating and understanding why nature matters will result in collective, or societal, decision-making that is more sustainable. Second, it is assumed that assessments of various forms of worth and value (e.g., cost) strongly influence individual behaviour. Third, assumptions about the connections between values and more individual-level behaviour are deeply rooted and omnipresent, so much so that some scholars have included behaviour in the definitions of some forms of value (Norton and Sanbeg 2020). These assumptions are often based on strong intuition, and they likely underlie many efforts to better understand and characterize environmental values.

Yet despite these intuitive assumptions that values and behaviour are tightly linked, research presents a much more complex picture of values-behaviour links. Scholarly research on the links between values and behaviour is enormously wide-ranging and multi-faceted; almost every social science discipline addresses this link in some way. Collectively these disciplines explore not only the more-discussed pathway from values to behaviour, but also how behaviour can influence values. This body of research also addresses the multiple (though tightly intertwined) meanings of value -- that is, “value of” (worth) and “values about” (principles).

Researchers who focus on how values may lead to behaviour in the environmental realm use the term “value-action gap” to refer to the observation that in many cases, people’s actions do not reflect their values (Blake 1999; Babutsidze & Chai, 2018; Flynn, Bellaby & Ricci, 2009). Yet this research is somewhat piecemeal; it includes a more theoretical paper that introduces the concept (Blake 1999) and a relatively small collection of empirical studies (e.g., Babutsidze & Chai, 2018; Chung & Leong, 2007; Flynn, Bellaby & Ricci, 2009) that specifically address the specific intersection of values and behaviour. Thus though the “values-behaviour gap” concept is widely cited (nearly 1500 times in just over twenty years), it has not been systematically explored -- either empirically or in terms of how it dialogues with much existing behaviour theory. The few empirical explorations indicate a complex reality (Chaplin et al. 2014).

This study approaches relationships between values and human action through a focus on theories of human behaviour. Specifically, it systematically analyses 134 theories of human behaviour and action for how they address values and value-adjacent constructs. Notably, as described below, the theories included in this analysis mostly focus on behavior, but a few also address how practices and actions may influence values.

Methods

Reviews upon which we based our analysis

For our core analysis, we conducted a “meta-review:” we used existing reviews of behaviour theories to both develop our list of theories and acquire information about each theory. We based our list of theories on two comprehensive reviews of theories of human behaviour. We focused on theories of human behaviour in general (rather than pro-environmental behaviour specifically) in order to include a much wider swath of scholarly research. The two reviews refined the lists of theories they address in different ways, and the lists they provide are thus highly complementary. Our list, which combines the lists from these two sources, thus includes a wide variety of behaviour theories deemed to be important across a wide array of contexts.

Our first source for behaviour theory was Michie et al.’s 2014 book on behaviour change theories. The authors, many of whom are involved in the medical field, used a combination of systematic literature review and expert knowledge to create the list of 83 behaviour theories that they review. First, they searched a selection of six professional scholarly databases (e.g., Econlit, International Bibliography of Social Sciences, MEDLINE). Their search included terms related behaviour change theory, specific behaviour theories, and behaviour change generally. Next, they conducted forward and backward searches based on results of their systems search. They then manually searched “key behavioural science journals”. As a final step to identify relevant theories, they consulted expert colleagues and “documents published by organisations with a known interest in behaviour change.” In their search, they excluded theories that only addressed group-level behaviour (e.g., organisational behaviour). Their search includes multiple health-specific theories, but it also includes scores of theories not specific to medicine (e.g., the Theory of Planned Behaviour, Value-Belief-Norm theory).

Our second source was Kwon and Silva’s 2020 systematic literature review of behavioural theories. The authors, who are involved in the planning field, used a regimented process to create the list of 62 behaviour theories that they review. First, they searched Web of Science for terms related to behaviour theory in the study title (including variations, e.g., behavioural and behaviour). Then they filtered these results to papers that met their definition of highly cited – a definition that varied based on the year of publication (with older papers needing a higher number of citations to qualify). Next, they classified papers according to the type of behaviour addressed, and they maintained only papers that addressed general human behaviour (as opposed to, for example, a specific health-related behaviour). They then screened papers to determine if multiple papers used the same theory (this happened roughly 30 times).

In addition to this core analysis, we also examined reviews of pro-environmental behaviour. These papers do not, in general, present theories of their own; instead, they summarize either empirical or theoretical work to synthesize its relevance to pro-environmental behaviour. Those that focus on a combination of empirical and theoretical work are listed in the main text. In addition, we reviewed Heimlich and Ardoin (2008); this paper is oriented toward an environmental audience, but summarizes general theories of behaviour change – not those specific to environmental issues. They summarize ten theories of behaviour, all of which are included in our core review.

A tendency toward individually focused theories

Because its list of theories is derived from reviews that use the search term “behaviour”, this study focuses primarily on theories that foreground individual behaviour. Yet as noted below, a few influential theories that do not focus on individual behaviour are included (e.g., Ostrom’s (1990) common pool resource theory; Latour’s (2005) actor-network theory; Coase’s (1937) transaction cost theory, which describes why firms form and has been influential in explaining organizational behaviour in general). This diverse collection of theories -- a relic of the use of the search term behaviour -- gives some sense of the broader scope of academic theories that address human action, but most strongly represents those with a primarily individual focus.

This characteristic of the present study mirrors environmentally focused literature that addresses human action. That literature also tends to highlight individual-level behaviour, while addressing the conceptual distinction between behaviour and action (Alisat & Riemer, 2015; Jensen, 2002). Research on “action” seems generally more associated with civic activity (e.g., requesting policy changes) than private, individual practices. Hence, the distinction concerns not only the role of social factors in forming individuals, but also the types of behaviour or action. It is noted that while many of the theories in this analysis attend to societal influences, they often take these as “given;” they do not focus on how values people hold reflect such influences, nor on how values are embedded in institutions that impact behaviour. These issues are further considered in the Discussion.

Analysis of constructs

Analysis began by compiling the theory lists from Michie et al. (2014; 83 theories) and Kwon and Silva (2020; 62 theories). A total of ten theories were duplicates (they appeared in both Michie et al. and Kwon and Silva). The final list thus included 134 theories¹.

Michie et al. (2014) include a multiple-page summary of each theory they review, and Kwon and Silva (2020) provide an Appendix that lists details about each theory. For theories that appeared in Michie et al., these summaries were used to complete database entries. We recorded basic information about the theory, such as its full name, authors, year published, associated discipline, and a brief summary. Each summary in Michie et al. (2014) begins with a bullet-pointed list of constructs involved; all constructs were entered in the database. For constructs that possibly would be coded as value-related, definitions drawn from the theory summaries were included in the database.

In Kwon and Silva’s appendix, constructs were listed with less standardized means and fewer details. For theories only in Kwon and Silva’s review (52 theories), a multi-step process was conducted to summarize constructs in each theory, in order to create construct lists analogous to those in Michie et al. (2014). This process involved four independent coders and two discussants/supervisors. The process was as follows.

¹ Behaviour theories literature review (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4399396>). For a full list of analysed theories see document (A) in

1. Training phase:

- a. All researchers examined Michie et al.'s construct lists and theory summaries to understand the way in which the constructs were used, parsed, and organized. This helped the team to reproduce the Michie et al. construct lists as closely as possible.
- b. Four of the original manuscripts that presented theories (as identified by Kwon and Silva (2020)) were selected as "training manuscripts". These manuscripts were selected to represent diverse types of original sources (e.g., books and articles, from different disciplines).
- c. All coders and discussants/supervisors read and coded these training manuscripts. The coding process involved identifying constructs important to the theory's function, description, or process, then including direct quotes or paraphrases to define each construct.
- d. Coding results from all researchers were combined, with agreements and disagreements noted.
- e. All researchers discussed every construct and its definition until agreement was reached on a final list of constructs for each theory.

2. Coding phase:

- a. Teams of two coders read a subset of original manuscripts. Each coder independently identified the constructs and definitions for each theory.
- b. The two lists of constructs were compared, with agreements and disagreements noted.
- c. The two coders and one discussant/supervisor met and discussed each construct in each theory until consensus was reached. Where the two coders disagreed (e.g., one had identified a particular construct and the other had not), the three researchers discussed how to proceed (e.g., whether the construct should be included). The team often revisited the original manuscripts during this discussion.

Once this coding process for the theories that appeared only in Kwon and Silva (2020) was completed, we combined this list of constructs with the list of constructs from Michie et al. (2014). This resulted in our final database of 2232 constructs. This list was first divided into constructs that were value-related and constructs that were not. The latter were classified as "all other constructs". This means that they were part of the behavioral theory, but no relation to values was evident from the name and how it was defined (see below and Table 2.29 for coding criteria).

After identifying which constructs were value-related and which were not, a deeper analysis of value-related constructs was conducted. This analysis considered broad values, specific values (both as defined in Section 2.2), and a set of considerations labelled as value-adjacent constructs. Value-adjacent constructs are those that are not directly broad or specific values, but in which principles or

importance (i.e., broad or specific values) play dominant roles (see Table 1). A codebook was developed based on definitions of value(s) in section 2.2. Constructs were identified as value-related when they met one of two criteria:

1. The words used to describe the construct (either in the construct name or in the description of the construct) included any of the terms in Table 1.
2. The construct's name or description fit with the definition of values in Section 2.2 – i.e., it related to principles, preferences, or priorities. In this case the constructs were categorized as “other value-related constructs” because they were generally uncommon (with one or sometimes two occurrences). They included terms like weights, gains or losses, and reasons.

Table 1. Categories of value-related constructs used in the analysis.

Concept	Relation to value
Attitude(s); attitudinal	Value-adjacent
Belief(s)	Value-adjacent
Cost(s); monetary	Value-adjacent
Desire(s)	Value-adjacent
Drive	Value-adjacent
Evaluation	Specific or value-adjacent
Goal(s)	Broad or specific values
Identity	Value-adjacent
Importance	Specific values
Mixed	Mixed
Moral; Morality	Broad values
Motivation; motivational	Value-adjacent
Need(s)	Value-adjacent
Norm(s); normative	Value-adjacent
Preference(s)	Value-adjacent
Priority(-ies)	Specific values
Rationality	Specific values
Rule(s)	Value-adjacent
Standards	Specific values
Value as principle (includes moral; morality)	Broad values
Value as worth	Specific values
Weight	Specific values

Distinctions between these categories are in some cases fluid. In addition to conceptual distinctions around the “edges” of these categories, it is also important to note that the theories we review define and cluster constructs in diverse ways. The analysis was as systematic as possible, but due to this diversity, results are best understood as approximate representations of the prevalence of various concepts.

The coding practice followed four rules: one primary and three secondary. The primary rule was that a construct was coded to the categories in Table 1 if the construct name or description included the term in Table 1. The first secondary rule was that if the construct name included only one of our focal terms, we coded it to that category, even if other terms were listed in the description. The next secondary rule was that we coded constructs as “mixed” under two conditions: the construct name included two focal terms (e.g., “Evaluation in respect to goals,” Self-Regulation Theory (Kanfer and Gaelick 1991)), or the construct name included no focal terms but the description included multiple focal terms. The third specific rule involved the “belief” category. Since the term “belief” frequently referred to beliefs unrelated to values (e.g., beliefs about effectiveness of receiving help, AIDS Risk Reduction Model (Catania et al. 1990)), whether the particular belief construct in the theory was value-related was assessed; only those that were value-related were included. In addition, because “belief” is the most inexact term in the construct list and was often paired with other items in our list in ways that did not add meaning, the following practice was implemented: whenever belief appeared with another focal concept, it was coded as the other concept. The construct “Normative beliefs,” for instance, was coded only to “norms”.

Results

Primary results are presented in the main text. We supplement those results with the following data and explanation.

It is interesting to examine co-occurrences between various value-related constructs (Figure 1). This examination reveals, for instance, that values as principle occur with almost every other construct (excluding cost or drive, which were more common in economically-oriented theories). It is the only construct for which this is true, which suggests that theories that address values as principles were likely to address value more holistically as well. This examination also reveals that the most common intersections (i.e., those with the largest numbers of theories) were norms with attitudes, and norms with other value-related constructs. These prevalences indicate both the wide reach and diverse application of norms and that norms and attitudes are often prominent parts of psychological theories.

It is also helpful to understand the relative distribution of value-related constructs between theories (Table 2). Concentrations of value-related constructs were fairly evenly distributed: for concentrations of zero constructs per theory up to seven constructs per theory, roughly 10-15% of theories appeared in each. Table 2 also clearly demonstrates a dramatic outlier theory, in terms of the number of value-related constructs included in it. Problem Behaviour Theory (Jessor 1987), contains 30 value-related constructs. This theory, which has 70 constructs total, includes 3 constructs which have value in the name of the construct (value of affection, value on independence, value on academic achievement), and a wide variety of other value-related constructs (e.g., father's religious group, parental ideology, peer influence. social criticism).

Figure 1. Co-occurrence of value-related constructs in theories. The number in each cell indicates the number of theories that contained constructs in both the row and column category for that cell. Shading is darker for larger numbers.

Table 2. Number of value-related constructs in theories.

# of value-related constructs in theory	# of theories
0	12
1	11
2	17
3	12
4	19
5	18
6	12
7	11
8	8
9	2
10	0
11	2
12	2
13	4
14	2
15	1
30	1

Discussion

The primary conclusions of this work are described in the main text.

An important additional point relates to the concept of the value-action gap, as mentioned in the main text and the introduction to this annex. This gap refers to values as principles. If, however, we use the definition of values in this assessment – i.e., that values are both broad and specific, and are embedded in institutions of many kinds – the gap could be considered to be much smaller. Our review supports the idea that the purported “value-action gap” is fairly large when we conceptualize values as principles. Yet our review suggests that -- at least in theory, according to theories of behaviour -- the value-action gap might be smaller if we conceptualize values more broadly. This suggests an area ripe for future research: If we conceptualize values as much more expansive than broad values, to include not only specific values but also value-adjacent concepts, does this change our understanding of the value-action gap?

Limitations of this analysis

One limitation of this analysis relates to the difficulty of precisely identifying and delimiting what constitutes constructs in each theory. As described above, our method included multiple practices that helped to systematize our identification and categorization of constructs. Yet this process is inherently complex, and our resulting list of constructs -- particularly from theories that only appeared in the Kwon and Silva (2020) paper -- should be considered an approximation of, rather than an irrefutable representation of, the concepts involved in each theory.

The primary limitation of this work relates to the different meanings of and literatures around the terms “Behaviour,” “Action”, and “Practices.” As noted in the main text, this analysis includes primarily theories that identify themselves as related to “behaviour.” None of the reviews we used focus on related terms that other fields use to denote human activity – primarily ‘action’ and ‘practices.’ ‘Behaviour’ is the term used more commonly in psychology, most branches of which focus on the individual human. Some researchers emphasize the conceptual distinction between behaviour and action (Jensen 2002, Alisat and Reimber 2015). This work notes that “behaviour” tends to focus more on personal practices (e.g., recycling or “responsible purchasing;” almost all of this research is conducted in developed countries), and it attends less frequently to social influences. Action, on the other hand, is generally more associated with civic activity (e.g., requesting policy changes), and attends more closely to social context. Yet another body of literature addresses practices (e.g., social practice theory, Bourdieu 1977); this body of theory heavily emphasizes the importance of social structure, context, and influence to determining human “practices” – i.e., why we do what we do. Researchers note that the focus on a narrow definition of behaviour can be a limitation when applied to environmental issues (Jensen 2002, Alisat and Reimber 2015). To further complicate this story, however, distinctions between behaviour and action are not clear-cut; one highly-cited typology of “environmentally significant behaviour” includes public-sphere, highly socially-constructed action as two of its three primary categories (Stern 2000).

Suggested future research

The most obvious future research direction that emerges from this study is to conduct a review of empirical studies that treat values-behavior links. Theories are often based on, or attempt to explain, empirical data, but they are fundamentally conceptual rather than evidence-based. A powerful followup study to this one would collate empirical studies that address relationships between values and behaviour (broadly construed, to include action, practices, and other related terms that are often treated differently in the literature).

Conclusion

Though a few more context-focused theories are included in this review, this analysis' focus on "behaviour theories" tilts our results toward theories that focus on the individual. Yet this review found that theories that address behaviour frequently included a variety of constructs related to social context and influence. Thus though it is important to note the limitations of the search strategy employed in this analysis, it is also important to note that the role of non-individual factors was strongly addressed in this analysis. This analysis thus provides a comprehensive summary of the role that value, defined broadly to include broad values, specific values, and value-adjacent constructs, plays in the complex suite of factors that relate to human action.

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